

Voice familiarity via training affects listening effort during a voice cue sensitivity task with vocoder degraded speech

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Abstract

Understanding speech in real-life can be challenging and effortful when multiple people speak at the same time. In speech-on-speech (SoS) perception, normal hearing (NH) listeners can use fundamental frequency (F0) and vocal-tract length (VTL) voice cues to separate speech streams, spoken by different talkers. However, such voice segregation can be challenging for cochlear implant (CI) users, as CI users have a reduced sensitivity to F0 and VTL voice cues. Additionally, vocoder studies show that listening effort is increased with increased spectral degradation in the speech signal. In SoS listening, familiarity with a talker's voice can improve speech intelligibility for NH listeners. However, it is unknown if voice familiarity improves sensitivity to F0 and VTL voice cues and affects listening effort, especially when the speech signal is vocoder degraded.

In this study, we aimed to provide voice familiarity by implicit short-term voice training. During training, participants listened to an audiobook segment of approximately 30 minutes that contained 13 chapters, and after each chapter, they answered a context related question. Voice sensitivity, namely just-noticeable-differences (JNDs) for F0 and VTL voice cues combined (F0+VTL), was measured with an odd-one-out task in a 3 alternative forced choice adaptive paradigm. Simultaneously, listening effort was measured via pupillometry.

Our results showed that voice training did not improve sensitivity to small F0+VTL voice cue differences measured at the threshold level for both non-vocoded and vocoded conditions. However, according to pupillometry results (analyzed with Generalized Additive Mixed Models), effort while listening to vocoded speech was less for trained (familiar) compared to untrained voices. These findings suggest that voice familiarity through implicit voice training can be of benefit for voice cue perception through reducing listening effort for vocoded speech, even in the absence of a behavioral effect, in the JNDs.

Introduction

When listening to multiple talkers at the same time, listening to familiar voices can provide a speech intelligibility benefit. A familiar voice that belongs to a partner or close friend can improve speech-on-speech (SoS) listening in normal hearing (NH) listeners (Holmes et al., 2018; Johnsrude et al., 2013). Additionally, it is possible to make a naïve listener familiar with a

previously unheard voice, through voice training. Voice training can be done explicitly, by training listeners with a speaker recognition task (Nygaard & Pisoni, 1998) or implicitly, through voice exposure over a period of time (Kreitewolf et al., 2017), similar to familiarizing with voices in real-life. It might be that the implicit knowledge we acquire about voices through exposure is related to talker-specific voice cues. Two main voice cues are fundamental frequency (F0) and vocal-tract length (VTL). While F0 is related to glottal pulse rate and perceived as the voice pitch, VTL is related to formant frequencies, and changes with the speaker's height. In SoS situations when there are clear differences in F0 and VTL between target and masker voices, intelligibility of the target speech is high (Darwin et al., 2003). However, when speech signals are inherently degraded via cochlear implants (CIs), F0 and VTL voice cues are not optimally perceived by the CI users, which contributes to the challenge of understanding speech in SoS situations (El Boghdady et al., 2019). Previous research showed that perceptual discriminability of F0 and VTL voice cues were limited with vocoder manipulations (Gaudrain & Başkent, 2015) and for CI users (Gaudrain & Başkent, 2018). While voice familiarity might improve speech intelligibility for NH listeners in SoS situations, where voice information is used to segregate target and masker speech, it is relatively unknown whether sensitivity to F0+VTL voice cues reduced by means of vocoding, would improve with voice training.

SoS perception is shown to be effortful in studies using pupillometry as an objective measure for listening effort (Koelewijn et al., 2012). Additionally, when speech is spectrally degraded, such as in CIs, listening also becomes more effortful (Winn et al., 2015), which contributes to the challenge of listening to speech in adverse conditions. As cognitive resources are limited, a reduction in listening effort would spare cognitive resources that can then be used for other listening related processes, which in turn might improve speech intelligibility (Rabbitt, 1966). Even though voice familiarity may show a benefit at behavioral level by improving speech intelligibility, our knowledge on how voice familiarity may affect listening effort remains scarce.

The present study investigated the effect of voice familiarity via implicit voice training, on F0+VTL voice cue discrimination and listening effort, when speech signal was non-vocoded and vocoded. Additionally, acoustic/linguistic variability of the stimuli was manipulated. After a short voice training, sensitivity to F0+VTL voice cues was measured by means of an adaptive procedure with just-noticeable-differences (JNDs) as the outcome measure, while in parallel, listening effort was assessed using pupillometry.

Methods

Participants

Sixteen NH native Dutch speaking adults between the ages of 21 and 39 years participated in the experiment. Participants with normal hearing audiometric thresholds were included in the study. At the beginning of the experimental session, a written informed consent was obtained from the participants. The ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the University Medical Center Groningen and participants received hourly compensation for their participation.

Stimuli

Stimuli for voice training

Stimuli used for voice training were auditory recordings of the first 13 chapters of "The Twits" (de Griezels) by Roald Dahl in Dutch language. A female native Dutch speaker took part in the recordings of the audiobook. From these recordings a male voice version was created by shifting the F0 -12 semitones (st) and shifting the VTL +3.8 st, as male voice was defined as having a difference of -12 F0 and +3.8 VTL difference from the original female voice (Gaudrain & Başkent,

2015, 2018). Female voice was also processed without shifting the F0 and VTL to keep the possible sound processing artifacts constant.

Stimuli for voice sensitivity and listening effort measurements

The same female Dutch speaker who took part in recordings of the audiobook for voice training, also took part in recordings of stimuli that were used during voice cue sensitivity measurements. We recorded meaningful Dutch CVC words from the Nederlandse Vereniging voor Audiologie (NVA) corpus (Bosman & Smoorenburg, 1995). The stimuli used during the voice sensitivity measurements were consonant-vowel triplets (CVCVCV) created from individual CVs that were extracted from the recorded CVC words. The procedure of extracting the CVs was similar to Gaudrain & Başkent (2015, 2018). During the adaptive task, while F0+VTL shifted versions of individual CVs were processed, CV durations were also equalized to 200 ms. CV triplets presented in one condition were either acoustic/linguistically the same (fixed item; such as BA-MI-BO, BA-MI-BO, BA-MI-BO) or different (variable item; such as BA-MI-BO, LE-MA-BE, DA-RE-MI), depending on the item variability condition. Stimuli were presented as either non-vocoded or vocoded signals. Vocoding manipulations were in line with Gaudrain & Başkent (2015), using settings that produce voice identification sensitivity performance matching that of highly performing CI users. A noise vocoder with 12-band, 12th order zero-phase bandpass filters between 150 and 7000 Hz was implemented, using Greenwood frequency-place mapping function for partitioning the cutoff frequencies of the filters. The temporal envelope was extracted with half-wave rectification and later low-pass filtered in each frequency band with a cutoff frequency of 300 Hz. Analysis and synthesis filters used the same settings. The vocoded signal was obtained by summing the output signal from all frequency bands.

Procedure

The experimental session started with voice training. Half of the participants listened to the first 13 chapters of “The Twits” uttered by the original female voice and the other half uttered by the simulated male voice. At the end of each chapter, a content related question was presented to ensure engagement. During voice training, participants did not receive any instructions to attend to the voice and training lasted approximately 30 minutes. Therefore, the implemented voice training was implicit and short term. An implicit voice training was chosen for this study, as an implicit voice training would be more similar to real life situations where exposure to a certain voice for some amount of time leads to voice familiarization. Voice training was followed by the voice discrimination task, which was similar to the procedure of Gaudrain & Başkent (2015, 2018). JNDs were obtained using an odd-one-out task in a 3 Alternative Forced Choice (AFC) adaptive paradigm, during which listeners chose the stimulus that sounded different (the target voice) than the other two stimuli that sounded identical to each other (the reference voice).

At the start of each trial, there was a 3 second silence, which was followed by the stimuli presentation. After the stimuli presentation, there was another 3 second silence. From the start of the trial until the end of 3 second silence after stimuli presentation, a fixation dot was presented in the center of the screen while x- and y- gaze data and pupil diameters of both eyes were recorded. Following pupillometry measurements, selection boxes numbered 1 to 3, referring to the order of the three CV triplets presented, was shown on the screen.

JNDs were measured using an adaptive procedure where target voice became closer to the reference voice by sifting the F0+VTL voice cues together using STRAIGHT software (Kawahara & Irino, 2005) in steps of 2 semitones (st), in a 2-down 1-up staircase procedure, that corresponded to 70.7% correct on the psychometric function. Step size was updated after 15 trials or after the voice difference became smaller than twice the step size by $\sqrt{2}$. JNDs were measured in two directions: from a target male voice towards a female reference voice and from a target female voice towards a male reference voice. The male voice was created by shifting the F0 by -12 semitones and the VTL by 3.8 semitones, the same parameters that were used during voice training. Target voice either belonged to the familiarized voice (female or simulated male

voice) or to an unfamiliar voice, which was the voice unused during training, either female or simulated male voice. At the end, all participants completed the JND test that consisted of the same 8 conditions, involving conditions with familiar or novel voice used as reference voice, where stimuli were either variable (3 acoustic-linguistically different stimuli) or fixed (3-acoustic linguistically same stimuli), presented as non-vocoded and vocoded signals.

Analysis

Voice sensitivity data analysis

F0+VTL JNDs were analyzed with a 2x2x2 repeated-measure analysis of variance (ANOVA) with voice training (untrained, trained voice), vocoder (non-vocoded, vocoded) and item variability (fixed, variable) as within-subject factors on the log-transformed JNDs, using R. Type I errors were corrected with False Discovery Rate (FDR).

Listening effort data analysis

Pupillometry measurements were first preprocessed, in line with Koelewijn et al. (2021). Trials containing 20% or more eye blinks were removed from further analysis. For the remaining trials, eye blinks were corrected with linear interpolation. Trials with eye movements outside of the visual display area were also excluded from further analysis. In order to remove high frequency artifacts, an 11-point moving average smoothing filter was used. A baseline value was calculated by taking the mean of the 1 s time window before stimulus onset. Baseline correction was performed by subtracting the trace's baseline value from the value for each time point within that trace. These preprocessed pupil traces were then averaged for each participant and each condition and Peak Pupil Dilation (PPD), Mean Pupil Dilation (MPD), Peak Pupil Dilation Latency (PPDL) and averaged baseline pupil diameter values were calculated. Between the time window of stimulus onset until response prompt, the maximum pupil dilation value in mm compared to baseline was calculated as PPD. MPD was calculated, within the same time window, as the average pupil dilation in mm relative to baseline and PPDL denotes the time in ms from the onset of stimulus until the PPD.

Separate 2x2x2 repeated measures ANOVAs were performed with voice training, vocoder and item variability as within-subject factors on each of the pupil outcome measures (PPD, MPD, PPDL and pupil baseline). In addition, a non-linear regression analysis was performed using Generalized Additive Mixed Models (GAMMs) to estimate the change in pupil dilation over time (van Rij et al., 2019), using R. Preprocessing of the data for GAMM analysis was performed the same way as described above with the exception of down-sampling data from 120 Hz to 30 Hz and not applying a smoothing filter. For GAMM analysis we pooled data over item variability conditions and performed planned comparisons between vocoder and voice training conditions. With GAMM analysis we looked at the change in pupil diameter over time with contrasts between the trained and untrained voices for both vocoded and non-vocoded speech signals. Contrasts between vocoded and non-vocoded speech for trained and untrained voices were also analyzed.

Results

Voice training

The answers to 13 multiple choice questions showed that the overall accuracy score was high (M= 88.94%, SD = 9.45%). Individual scores from participants also showed that no participant scored lower than 76.92% correct. These high accuracy scores demonstrate that listeners were attentive during voice training.

Voice sensitivity

Figure 1 displays the log transformed F0+VTL JNDs for levels of different conditions, including voice training, vocoder and item variability.

Figure 1 — Voice cue sensitivity in F0+VTL JNDs for conditions of voice training (untrained, trained), item variability (fixed, variable) and vocoder (non-vocoded, vocoded) is shown. JNDs shown in the y-axis are plotted on a logarithmic scale. The boxes illustrate the upper and lower quartiles, and the median is represented as the midline of the boxes.

The results show that vocoder manipulations had a main effect on the JNDs [$F_{(1,15)} = 346.74, p < 0.001, \eta^2_g = 0.69$]. When vocoded signals were presented, on average, JNDs were significantly larger (7.33 st) than when non-vocoded signals were presented (1.45 st). The second largest main effect was observed with item variability manipulations [$F_{(1,15)} = 65.03, p < 0.001, \eta^2_g = 0.21$]. When variable items were presented, average JNDs were significantly larger (5.80 st) than when fixed items were presented (2.99 st). Contrary to expectation, voice training did not have a significant main effect on the JNDs [$F_{(1,15)} = 1.16, p = 0.298, \eta^2_g = 0.00$].

There was a significant interaction between vocoder and item variability conditions on the JNDs, [$F_{(1,15)} = 8.82, p < 0.05, \eta^2_g = 0.01$]. A pairwise t-test was conducted for multiple comparisons and results showed that item variability conditions (variable vs fixed) were significantly different from each other in non-vocoded conditions [$t_{(15)} = 5.38, p_{FDR} < 0.001$], and in vocoded conditions [$t_{(15)} = 8.43, p_{FDR} < 0.001$]. More specifically, the difference between the fixed and variable JNDs was larger for vocoded (5.68 st) than for non-vocoded (0.57 st) conditions, which explains the interaction. There were no other significant interactions.

Listening effort

ANOVA results

Figure 2 displays the pupil dilation response (mm) over time, where pupil traces were averaged over all participants and per conditions.

Figure 2 — Mean pupil dilation (mm) over time (sec) for all conditions is shown. Time window between -1 and 0 seconds is denoted as the baseline and pupil dilation response to stimuli presentation is illustrated from seconds 0 to 6.5. Solid lines represent untrained voices and dashed lines represent trained voices.

As shown in Figure 2, pupil dilation responses were larger when speech was vocoded, compared to non-vocoded, which was also shown by a significant main effect of vocoder on the PPD [$F_{(1,15)} = 14.82, p < 0.01$], MPD [$F_{(1,15)} = 10.90, p < 0.01$] and on PPDL [$F_{(1,15)} = 7.50, p < 0.05$]. According to ANOVA results, there was no significant main effect of voice training on the PPD [$F_{(1,15)} = 2.38, p = 0.144$], MDP [$F_{(1,15)} = 1.31, p = 0.270$] or PPDL [$F_{(1,15)} = 0.72, p = 0.409$]. There was also no significant main effect of item variability on PPD [$F_{(1,15)} = 0.00, p = 0.976$], MPD [$F_{(1,15)} = 0.06, p = 0.812$] or PPDL [$F_{(1,15)} = 0.01, p = 0.945$]. However, item variability had a significant effect on the baseline pupil dilation [$F_{(1,15)} = 12.67, p < 0.01$]. During baseline period, pupil dilation responses were significantly larger when variable items were presented compared to fixed items. There was also a significant interaction between item variability and vocoder conditions on the baseline [$F_{(1,15)} = 4.88, p < 0.05$]. Multiple comparisons showed that variable and fixed items were significantly different from each other when the signal was vocoded [$t_{(28,7)} = 3.95, p_{FDR} < 0.001$], and no significant difference between levels of item variability condition was observed when the signal was non-vocoded [$t_{(28,7)} = 0.51, p_{FDR} = 0.616$]. There were no other significant interactions on the pupil outcome measures.

GAMM analysis results

We carried out GAMM analysis to assess pupil dilation response over time. With GAMM analysis smooth functions are fitted to the data and the relationship between conditions can be non-linear. GAMM analysis provides a possibility of assessing pupil dilation over time, instead of using outcome measures such as PPD, MPD and PPDL as dependent variables. Details of performing GAMM analysis with pupillometry data can be found at van Rij et al. (2019).

We looked at the pupil dilation response over time between voice training and vocoder conditions as a planned comparison, by pooling over data from item variability, since item variability had no effect on the pupil dilation response during the stimuli presentation.

Figure 3 — GAMM analysis results for untrained and trained voices within non-vocoded and vocoded conditions are shown. Estimated effects of trained and untrained voices in vocoded and non-vocoded conditions are plotted in the estimated effects plot. Estimated differences in pupil dilation responses across time are plotted for contrasts of untrained and trained voices when speech is non-vocoded and vocoded, with pointwise 95% confidence intervals. The time period where the estimated difference in pupil dilation between the untrained and trained voices significantly differs from the 0 line is indicated by the red line in the lower right panel x-axis.

Figure 3 shows the estimated differences in the pupil dilation between untrained and trained voices for non-vocoded and vocoded conditions. The red line on the below panel of Figure 3 illustrates the deviation from the 0 line. Visual inspection of Figure 3 shows that when the speech signal was vocoded, pupil dilation was significantly larger when listening to untrained voice compared to trained voice. There was no significant difference between pupil dilation response

to untrained and trained voices when speech signal was non-vocoded. This difference was confirmed by Ordered Factor Difference (OFD) statistics ($p = 0.034$).

Figure 4— GMM analysis results showing differences in pupil dilation responses across time for contrast between non-vocoded and vocoded speech for untrained and trained voices is shown, with pointwise 95% confidence intervals. The time period where the estimated difference in pupil dilation between the non-vocoded and vocoded speech significantly differs from the 0 line is indicated by the red line in the lower panel x-axis of the plot.

Figure 4 shows the contrast between non-vocoded and vocoded speech for untrained and trained voices. Visual inspection of Figure 4 and the OFD statistics shows that pupil dilation responses to vocoded and non-vocoded voices were significantly different when voices were both untrained and trained. However, OFD statistics also showed an interaction between training and vocoding ($p = 0.031$), which indicates that estimated differences (contrasts) for non-vocoding and vocoding in pupil dilations were smaller for trained voices than for untrained voices. Deviance explained from the final model was 77.1%.

Discussion

The present study examined the effect of voice training, as a way of providing voice familiarity, on voice sensitivity through F0+VTL voice cue discrimination and listening effort. Acoustic linguistic variability of the stimuli was manipulated with the item variability condition by presenting variable or fixed items. Additionally, stimuli were either vocoded or non-vocoded.

Our results showed that voice training did not influence voice cue discriminability. Sensitivity to small differences in F0+VTL, at threshold level, did not improve with voice familiarity. It is possible that other covarying voice cues such as pitch contour and speaking rate might have additionally been in use during voice discrimination. Therefore, voice discrimination based only

on using F0+VTL voice cues might not be sufficient to observe a familiarity benefit. GAMM analysis performed as a planned comparison showed that voice training had an effect on the pupil dilation response only when speech was vocoded. Pupil dilations were larger, indicating more effort, when listening to untrained vocoded voices than listening to trained vocoded voices. This effect lasted almost the entire duration of the stimulus presentation, from 2 seconds until 5.5 seconds. However, we did not see the effect of voice training on the pupil dilation response, when speech was non-vocoded. This suggests that, when speech is vocoded and input demands were high, voice familiarity might have acted like a compensatory mechanism for perception of degraded speech (Başkent et al., 2016). The results from both contrasts shown in Figures 3 and 4 indicated that trained voices were less affected by vocoding. Listening effort decreased for trained voices compared to untrained voices when speech was vocoded, while the contrast between vocoded and non-vocoded speech was also smaller for trained voices, compared to untrained voices.

As expected, vocoded speech resulted in significantly poorer discrimination of F0+VTL voice cues. Additionally, increased acoustic linguistic variability through variable item presentation also hindered voice cue discrimination performance. There was also an interaction between item variability and vocoder conditions. JNDs were significantly larger (performance was worse) when variable items were presented compared to fixed items when speech was both vocoded and non-vocoded, and the difference in variable item vs fixed item JNDs were larger for vocoded conditions than non-vocoded conditions.

Pupillometry data showed that listening to vocoded signals resulted in significantly larger pupil dilation response, reflected by PPD, MPD and PPDL. Winn et al. (2015) showed that while understanding speech, listening effort increased with decreased number of spectral bands in a vocoder which increases signal degradation. In addition to findings of Winn et al. (2015), our results show that pupil dilation responses were larger with vocoder manipulations during voice discrimination. Item variability was shown to only affect the pupil baseline, which, according to the adaptive gain theory (Aston-Jones & Cohen, 2005), can be interpreted as an increase in anticipated task difficulty, when variable items were presented compared to fixed items. The interaction between vocoder and item variability in the pupil baseline shows that anticipation of increased task difficulty specifically happened when speech was vocoded and variable items were presented, which was indeed the hardest condition in the experiment.

Together our findings suggest that voice familiarity through implicit voice training, which is similar to becoming familiar with specific voices in real life, can be of benefit at the level of voice cue perception through reducing listening effort for vocoded speech. This way CI users might benefit from spared cognitive resources which can be used for other listening related tasks such as understanding speech, remembering what was being said, and voice discrimination.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Etienne Gaudrain for experimental software, data analysis and helpful discussions on study design; Terrin Tamati for helpful discussions on study design. This study was funded by the VICI grant 918-17-603 from the Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO) and the Netherlands Organization for Health Research and Development (ZonMw), Heinsius Houbolt Foundation, and the Rosalind Franklin Fellowship.

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Comments

Comments from Anne Caclin:

In this interesting paper, the authors assess whether familiarity with a voice can improve voice cue sensitivity and listening effort during voice discrimination (using vocoded and non-vocoded speech). Below are some suggestions for minor clarifications.

- Lines 29-30: this sentence is difficult to understand. I suggest to emphasize what is analyzed (pupil dilation as a measure of the listening effort) rather than the analysis method.
 - We agree with the reviewer, however we decided to specifically mention the analysis because we couldn't find such an effect with the analysis of other measures of pupil data (such as ANOVAs with PPD, MPD and PPDL as dependent variables). Therefore, the sentence that was pointed out by the reviewer is now changed, although it still incorporates the analysis method. (line 29, page 1)
- Line 32-33: perhaps clarify that "behavioral effect" pertains to JNDs for the discrimination of voices.
 - We agree with the reviewer and this sentence is modified accordingly. (line 33, page 1)
- Pages 2-3: I suggest to explain in more details that a continuum was created between the two voices (male and female), how it was done, and how it is used during the experiment.
 - Additional explanations added on lines 131-133, page 3.
- Lines 129-130: perhaps remind the reader here what is meant by "variable or fixed".
 - A reminder about fixed and variable items is added on lines 137-138, page 4.
- Line 179: clarify what is meant by "largest main effect".
 - This part of the sentence is deleted.
- Line 186-190: the post-hoc tests reported do not allow to understand the interaction between Vocoder condition and Item variability. I suggest to compute differences between performance under the two vocoder conditions and compare them across Item variability conditions (or the reverse). It should then be possible to better interpret this interaction (Lines 274-279).
 - We agree with the reviewer and a better explanation of the interaction is added on lines 197-199, page 5.
- Lines 219-221: I did not understand the logic of pooling data across Item variability. Is it based on the analyses presented above? But in these analyses, there is no significant effect of Voice familiarity, which will turn out to be significant in the GMM analysis, which hence seems more sensitive. Please clarify.
 - According to the ANOVAs, item variability was shown to affect the baseline and not the event-related pupil response. Therefore, we pooled the data to do a planned comparison between vocoder and voice training, which simplified the interpretation of the results and increased the statistical power. Additionally, when item variability was not pooled, GMM analysis results were similar to what is reported here. The full model showed that there was only a significant difference on the pupil dilation responses between trained and untrained voice conditions, when both fixed and variable items were presented in vocoded speech. In addition, there was no significant difference between pupil responses to trained and untrained voices for both fixed and variable items when speech was non-vocoded. Therefore, the sensitivity of the GMM analysis results is more to do with the analysis method than the pooling.

Comments from Richard McWalter:

This was a beautifully written article. The experiment design was clever and the use of additional metrics (i.e. pupillometry) to investigate the effects of voice familiarity was very nice. It's quite difficult to study the effects of speech training on SoS in normal hearing listeners, let alone CI users, and I think the use of the vocoder was well implemented. I found the results to be intriguing, as there was little to no change in behavioral performance but a large change in listening effort as shown by changes in pupil diameter.

I was wondering if there would be any change if the listeners were trained on vocoded speech rather than processed real speech. Presumably, CI users would be training on the signal that is

input to their auditory system/brain, which might be more akin to vocoded speech. I'm not sure if training NH listeners on vocoded speech makes sense though :/

One thing I have always noticed with my friends with CIs is that sometimes the familiarity with the talkers facial movements seems important. For example, my close friend would sometimes ask me to repeat a sentence from an unfamiliar talker. I especially noticed this to be the case when the unfamiliar talker was a non-native speaker. But perhaps this is more to do with talker voice familiarity (as the paper might suggest) than other, non-auditory cues, such as facial/mouth movements.

Again, this was a very well written paper and interesting finding.

- We thank the reviewer for his kind words and the insights on how CI users might perceive speech from unfamiliar speakers and non-native speakers. We implemented this study as a first step to investigate how short-term voice training might affect voice cue discrimination and listening effort. Therefore, adding a vocoder condition provides very important insights on how the actual cochlear implant users might perform and exert effort. As a next step, we would like to work with cochlear implant users, and based on these results and a follow-up study we conducted recently, we have a good starting point and more concrete hypotheses on what to expect when voice training will be done with cochlear implant users. The question if training normal hearing listeners with vocoded speech would have resulted in a different outcome is a good one. Participants would have been more adapted to listening to the trained voice being vocoded as during the JND task. This could indeed lead to different outcomes and is important for us to keep in mind when performing a similar kind of study on CI users.

A few small comments:

Line 103: Simple technical question. How was the synthesis performed? Were the subbands simply summed together?

- The vocoded signal was obtained by summing the output signal from all frequency bands. (lines 104-105, page 3)

Line 113: Were the "same" conditions identical waveforms, or was it a different exemplar of the same reference voice?

- The same conditions were identical waveforms.

Line 216: This sentence reads a bit weird, as if it's switching between tenses.

- We agree with the reviewer and the pointed sentences are now modified. (lines 225-226, page 6)

Line 223: I'm not sure it's mentioned what the shaded regions are (e.g. standard error of the mean, standard deviation)?

- The shaded area represents pointwise 95% confidence intervals. This is now added on the captions of Figures 3 and 4.

Comments from Mengchao Zhang:

The paper examined whether a short 30-minute training to get familiarized with a voice could facilitate voice discrimination performance compared to discriminating an untrained voice and examined whether the training effect would differ when the speech was either naturally uttered or vocoded. Voice stimuli was manipulated by changing the fundamental frequencies F0 and the vocal-tract length (VTL). The study also examined pupillometry data under these conditions to capture the impact of voice familiarity and vocoding on listening effort during the voice discrimination task. The short-term familiarization of voice did not seem to impact voice discrimination performance, but did somehow affect pupil dilation.

This is an interesting study. Here are the comments regarding the details of the paper:

- Line 95-96: an example of a fixed and a variable item will be helpful.
 - Examples for variable and fixed item presentations are added. (lines 95-96, page 3)

- Line 99: why did you pick 12 channels instead of 22 or 24 which are more commonly used in CI patients? And do you predict that there will be any changes in behavioral or pupillometry data with more channels (richer spectral cues)?
 - We wanted to replicate the vocoder condition from Gaudrain & Baskent (2015) to have a baseline of JNDs that might be expected with normal hearing listeners. Note that vocoding and CI processing differ in the fact that vocoder bands each present an independent part of the sound spectrum which are then presented at the same time. This is not the case for the electrical pulses sent through CI channels. These pulses are not necessarily based on separate spectral bands or presented at the same time, but instead depend on the processing algorithm/strategy used in the CI. Therefore, a 12-band vocoder was chosen to simulate good CI performance. Additionally, most CIs have 12 channels however only a few CI brands use 22-24 bands.
- Line 109: Perceptual learning studies have often raised the importance of the amount of initial training which needs to reach some critical value to induce perceptual learning. Would 30 minutes be enough as an initial training amount to induce perceptual learning of a voice? As the vocoded voice was not learned (and often needs learning at least for speech recognition), could the increased pupil dilation a reflection of perceptually learning of vocoded voice or/and increased listening effort?
 - According to a study from Holmes et al., 2021, an intelligibility benefit of voice training is shown even after 10 minutes of training. This intelligibility benefit however, was shown to increase by longer duration of voice training. For the second question. In this study, when we look into the effect of voice training between vocoded and non-vocoded speech conditions, we see that, according to the GAMM analysis results, there was a significant difference between pupil responses to trained and untrained voices when both of these voice were vocoded. Therefore, it is unlikely that this effect reflects learning of a new, vocoded voice since there is a significant difference in the pupil dilation between two vocoded voices.
- Line 115-120: A figure (to show the timeline of the stimuli, pupillometry recording windows, and a behavioral response window) will be helpful.
 - We agree with the reviewer, however the proceeding is already very long and we decided that one more figure might clutter it. For a more detailed explanation of the design, where a timeline of an experimental trial is also shown, we refer the reviewer to the relevant publication, Biçer et al., 2023.
- Line 123: what is '2 st'? Also, what are the step sizes of the F0 and VTL, respectively?
 - We would like to thank the reviewer for pointing this out. "St" denotes semitones. We changed that on the manuscript (line 127, page 3). During the experiment, we changed the F0 and VTL semitones together and not separately, by 2 steps. The step size was also updated after 15 trials.
- Line 128: How are the conditions balanced across participants?
 - Everyone completed the same 8 conditions. We made this point clearer at line 135-136, page 4.
- Line 130-131: Would you kindly provide more details on the unfamiliar voice (e.g. F0, VTL, etc.)? How different is it from the trained voice? Are the untrained voice and the reference voice intermediate F0+VTL between the trained female and the simulated male voices? What's the initial F0+VTL of the adaptive procedure, the female voice?
 - The unfamiliar voice was either a female voice or a simulated male voice. This unfamiliar voice was created by shifting the F0 by -12 semitones and VTL by 3.8 semitones. As during voice training either of these voices (female or simulated male voice) were used, and therefore was the trained voice, for participants who received training with the female voice, the untrained voice was the simulated male voice (which was used as trained voice for other participants) and vice versa. An additional explanation is added on lines 131-133, page 3.

Comments from Daniel Oberfeld:

Interesting study, very clear and well planned!

I only have a few minor questions/comments.

l 95 Some examples would be nice

- We agree with the reviewer and some examples of the fixed and variable items are added. (lines 95-96, page 3)

l 111 What was the motivation for choosing such a rather implicit training procedure? And would you expect the results to differ if the training was more explicit?

- We thank the reviewer for this comment, as the chosen training method is an important factor in our results. We chose to implement an implicit voice training as it is more similar to how humans become familiar with a voice, through exposure to a certain voice for some amount of time. That being said, if the training was more explicit, the results might have differed. Because the learning mechanisms would be different. We added our motivation on why choosing an implicit voice training on lines 112-114, page 3.

l 200 Figure 2 does not really plot the DVs you're analyzing here. So additional plots of the actual DVs (e.g., similar to Figure 1) would be informative

- The figure 2 shows the pupil dilation for each condition and it is averaged across conditions and participants. Therefore, from this plot, the peak (max pupil dilation), the peak pupil dilation latency (at what time the peak is reached for each condition), the mean pupil dilation and the baseline interval (time point from -1 to 0 seconds) are all visible from this plot.

l 215 I do not really understand what this analysis is doing/looking for. I guess the time course of the pupil dilation is modeled by a nonlinear function, and then effects of the independent variables on this time course are analyzed. But a description of what this modeling does would be necessary to understand the analysis. I was also wondering: if you'd simply divide the pupil responses into successive time windows of, say 1 s, and then make the time window a factor in addition to your IVs, would that simpler analysis show a similar result? The plots in Figures 3 and 4 suggest that what you're interested in are simply shifts in the amplitudes between, e.g., untrained versus trained - that should also surface in the simpler "windowed" analysis.

- We would like to thank the reviewer for this comment. We did write what the analysis does more in detail now (lines 227-228, page 6) but for more details about doing GAMM analysis on pupillometry data, we refer the readers to van Rij et al., 2019. For the second part of the question, it may be indeed possible to see an effect with a time window analysis. The reason why we preferred to assess pupil dilation over the time course is that because during listening participants will need to remember the three items presented and the odd-one-out might come up in the first item or the last might lead to changes in the pupil dilation and we did not want to incorporate this effect into our analysis. However, time windows of for example 1 second, might reflect the effect of the timing of odd-one-out stimulus. Finally, we would like to note that the GAMM has shown to be a much more powerful statistical analysis than an ANOVA when it comes to pupil data.

Discussion: In the introduction you mention studies that did find an effect of training on discriminability of voices. Why do you think you did not find this effect here, what were the differences of these previous studies?

- We would like to thank the reviewer for this comment. We mention two studies on the effect of voice training in Introduction. These are Nygaard & Poisoni, 1998 and Kreitewolf et al., 2017. Both of these studies measured intelligibility performance and not voice discrimination performance. That being said, Nygaard & Poisoni, 1998 used an explicit voice training where talker identity knowledge was learned, which was different from the current study. Kreitewolf et al., 2017 implemented an implicit voice training, which is more similar to this study. However, the authors implemented a training for 4 days, and used the same type of stimuli (sentences) for both voice training and test, in addition to measuring intelligibility rather than voice discrimination. Therefore, because of methodological differences mentioned above, a training effect on a different task (voice discrimination), might have led to a lack of voice training effect.

Comments from Anna Dietze:

The presented study is very interesting and the paper is easy to read.

I only have some minor questions/comments:

Is there also some effect of male vs. female voice?

- Thank you for the question. We did not check for a difference between female and male voices. Note that male and female voice is simply a labeling used. What we refer to as the male voice stimuli, were created by changing F0 and VTL voice cues of the original stimuli that were uttered by a female talker. Hence, an effect of male vs. female voice in this study would not be generalizable and therefore not be interpreted as actual effect of male vs. female voice. Instead it can only be interpreted as the effect of changes in the F0 and VTL voice cues.

l 185 can eta squared be 0.00 or would it rather be <0.01?

- As eta squared values are reported as they are, using an equal sign, we reported the results exactly as ANOVA results were, using the R software.

l188 for the interaction it would be nice if you also stated that the difference between fixed and variable conditions was larger in the vocoded condition.

- As suggested by the reviewer, an explanation of the interaction is added. (lines 197-199, page 5)

Figure 2 I wondered about the variability across the 16 subjects

- There was indeed variability across subjects. However, plotting individual data is very messy (reflecting physiological variance between participants rather than effort) and therefore not very informative and not a common practice in pupillometry data analysis.

Figure 3 I think here dashed and dotted lines correspond to exactly the different condition compared to Figure 2. In addition, I do not understand why everything in this Figure is called 'estimated'. Can you clarify this?

- We would like to thank the reviewer for bringing this into our attention. In these plots, estimated means that the differences in the pupil responses between the two conditions are estimated by the model.

Figure 4 What does the shaded area indicate?

- The shaded area represents pointwise 95% confidence intervals. This is now added on the figure captions of Figures 3 and 4.

l277 From the description it sounds more like a general main effect of fixed vs. variable instead of the interaction effect you are talking about. Can you specify what exactly the interaction does? (Larger difference in the vocoded condition?)

- We agree with the reviewer and a more detailed explanation of the interaction is added on lines 290-291, page 9.

l282 Does decreased spectral bands mean a decreased number of bands or decreased bandwidth?

- It means decreased number of spectral bands. We added this information on line 294, page 9.

Up-to-date comments can be found on [PubPeer](#).